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Cross-Cultural Communication:
**Translational Context of African Tonal
Languages in the West**

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Abstract

In the current study, I investigate the obstacles inherent in translating African tonal languages, focusing on the Beninese Fon, into French. The Fon tonal system, made up of diacritical marks and tonal spelling, complicates the realization of an equitable translation and effective cultural mediation. In this research, I aim to explore how Fon tonal features manifest in writing and identify the linguistic and cultural issues involved in translating these tonal elements, within the context of Séverin-Marie Kinhou's essay, *Anonugbe: La langue maternelle*. Considering the translation outcomes, I employ the Carl James' framework of Contrastive Analysis to evaluate the translation of the Fon tonal features into French. Given that both Western and African readers are targeted by the *Anonugbe: La langue maternelle*'s translation, I examine, from Carl James' perspective, the possible implications of the product for the diverse readerships. The findings show that deploying context-sensitive strategies in the successful mediation of tonal variabilities is necessary for promoting effective, intercultural understanding and diplomacy between the African and Western languages.